

PRACTICAL-TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM FOR IMPROVING THE USE OF TECHNOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN THE COGNITIVE PROCESS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15766187>

Abstract. *In today's world where we keep getting hit with different kinds of information in various platforms, it is not unusual to keep finding ourselves thinking more and more about how to pick out accurate information from a sea of non-fact-based information or bias opinions. There are many patterns in our living habits which should be re-evaluated, changed, or leave in the past entirely. It is easier said than done. For human nature, change seems scary. The uncertainty of not knowing the outcome makes us want to stick with old habits. Here lays one of the reasons for difficulties in seeing the flaws in our doings and changing our behavior. This would mean a change needs to happen.*

With all more reason, we must pay attention to our critical thinking skills. If we all were efficient critical thinkers, we would have the skill to evaluate our learned daily patterns or information given to us. Thinking critically, we are able to get to clearer fact-based conclusions on what we believe and make connection to where our values lay. Mastering a skill to think and evaluate information is not the only thing needed for us to change our ways, but it sure is an efficient way to start.

According to the results of the conducted scientific theoretical analyses, the possibilities, importance and scientific methodological foundations of developing critical thinking in the cognitive process of preschool children have not been fully revealed. This, in turn, indicates the relevance of researching the methodology for developing critical thinking in the cognitive process of preschool children.

Keywords: *cognitive process, education, tendency, critical thinking.*

INTRODUCTION.

Modern requirements for the level of development of preschool children, the emergence of difficulties in children's critical thinking necessitated the conduct of this research work. In preparing children for school education, it is important to improve the content and methodology of developing their mental potential, cognitive process. Therefore, the systematization of effective methods and technologies for the formation of skills and qualifications of the cognitive process of children of the preparatory group in preschool education has emerged as an urgent issue facing the national preschool pedagogy. In our study, the development of a pedagogical model for the development of critical thinking in the cognitive process of children of the preparatory group in preschool educational organizations was identified as a priority task. Based on this model, it is envisaged to study the importance of the influence of family, society and social environment in the development of critical thinking of children aged 6-7. In addition, attention is paid to improving methods that develop children's critical thinking in the educational process.

During the initial experimental work dedicated to substantiating the relevance of the research topic, it was observed that children in the preparatory group for school could not adequately answer even simple questions about critical thinking. It was found that most of them were only adapted to question and answer. It was shown that children do not have the skills to think independently, express their personal point of view, analyze information, and sort it in the process of communication. The analysis of the experimental work showed that children aged 6-7 years old cannot determine their own desires, interests, and wishes, do not have sufficient knowledge about proposing and defending ideas, independently organizing their activities based on important elements of their nationality, and the obligations assigned to them, which is directly related to the professional skills of educators.

Jean-Jacques Piaget, a scientist who studied the thinking of preschool children, found that the thinking of a 6-7-year-old child has the following features: children do not have formed ideas about the space of the main properties of objects, that is, they do not understand the principle of conservation, they do not take into account several properties of an object at the same time and compare their changes, they focus on only one thing, the most obvious property, while ignoring the rest.

Critical thinking teaches a person to act actively, make decisions, and understand how to act in accordance with the information received, which requires not only the ability to think internally, but also the ability to discuss and communicate with other people. It develops communication skills, the ability to find and analyze information, and teaches objective and comprehensive thinking.

LITERATURE REVIEW. Critical thinking and criticality may have a negative ring to it, but it surely is not done in negative intentions. According to McKean critical thinking origins can be traced back to early Greek philosophy and language. The word critical comes from a word “kritikos” and the definition of criticality is strongly attached to ideology of reasoning and making good judgements. Psychologist, philosopher, and the father of modern-day critical thinking John Dewey defines critical thinking as following: “*Active, persistent, careful consideration of a belief or supposed form of knowledge in light of the grounds that support it and the further conclusions to which it tends*” This quote refers to critical thinking as a tool to explore and explain one's beliefs by leaning on facts. Critical thinking is seen as an asset and important developing target in the education field. However, there are mixed opinions amongst educators on the definition and development of critical thinking.

To form an understanding of varying views, critical thinking can be looked through five well-known philosophers' eyes and their ideology: Robert Ennis, Richard Paul, John McPeck, Harvey Siegel and Jane Roland Martin. There are some differences in the discussion about criticality and what makes an efficient critical thinker. Some ideas suggest that the most important way to look at critical thinking is seeing criticality as a skill, which should be learned and developed. Some on the other hand emphasize criticality as a character trait or just knowledge on particular topic. Amongst these philosophers Ennis and Paul gravitate towards skills for critical reasoning, McPeck to particular discipline and thorough knowledge on topic.

Research shows that the process of critical thinking consists in not placing limits or prohibitions on the child's development and abilities. In the West, this phenomenon S. L. Rubinstein, J. Piaget, D. Bruner, L. S. Vygotsky, R. Paul, K. Popper, E. Glasser, D. Johnson, D. A. Braus, D. Byde, D. Halpern, M.N. Brown, Dj. Cheffey, Ch. Templen, K. Meredikt, D. Steele,

S. Walter, K. Adamson, S. Brookfield, S. I. Veksler, V. A. Shams, R. Paul, etc., were studied by a number of pedagogues.

Today, in various scientific sources, you can find different definitions of the term "critical thinking". J. Brous and D. Wood define it as intelligent, reflective thinking aimed at deciding what to believe and what to do. Critics are trying to understand and realize their own self, to be objective, logical, and to understand other points of view. Critical thinking, according to them, is the search for common sense: "how to judge objectively and act logically, taking into account your own point of view and the opinions of others, abandoning your own prejudices ability. Critical thinkers can come up with new ideas and see new possibilities, which is essential in solving problems."

D. Halpern [2] in his book "The Psychology of Critical Thinking" defines critical thinking as follows: it is "directed thinking that is balanced, logical and purposeful, characterized by the use of such cognitive skills and strategies, it increases the probability of achieving the desired result.

Educator E. Glasser developed a critical thinking program that includes tests for reasoning, drawing conclusions, recognizing assumptions, evaluating the strength of conclusions and arguments. According to him, critical thinking is the ability to evaluate the validity of judgments, to approve actions and their level of validity, to find a specific limit of their application.

Richard Paul [1], one of the leading scientists of the USA in the field of theory and practice of critical thinking, believes that the concept of critical thinking can be defined in different, non-contradictory ways. With this in mind, he gives this definition: "Critical thinking is thinking about thinking, where one reflects on one's own thinking with the goal of improving it."

M.N. Brown defines critical thinking as a special type of thinking that focuses on evaluating ideas. In a narrow sense, it is related to checking the accuracy of statements and the correctness of judgments. According to him, the uniqueness of critical thinking is largely determined by its questioning position, which is explained in the following points:

- to know a set of interrelated critical issues;
- the ability to ask critical questions and quickly respond;
- the desire to actively use critical questions.

American philosopher and educator John Dewey believes that critical thinking occurs when children begin to deal with a specific problem. "The main question to be asked about a situation or phenomenon, taken as the starting point of the learning process, is the question of what problems this phenomenon creates" [5]. According to Dewey, preschoolers are encouraged to think critically by focusing on problems and being naturally curious. "Only by struggling with a particular problem, by finding a way out of a difficult situation, does one really think." Thus, by critical thinking, Dewey means reflection.

Therefore, one aspect of critical thinking is manifested in reflecting, perceiving and evaluating the opinions of others and one's own. The second aspect of critical thinking is related to knowledge. In this case, critical thinking performs evaluation tasks: the origin of knowledge, its reliability and validity are evaluated, knowledge is interpreted and understood, and conclusions or conclusions are drawn based on it. Thus, the result of critical thinking can be a decision, a point of view, a proposal, a new approach to a decision. However, critical thinking does not fully reflect it, even though it includes it.

K. Popper considered the basis of critical thinking to be an attitude of readiness to change, verify and reject. "It is not the possession of knowledge that makes a person a scientist, but his constant and courageous pursuit of truth. Whatever solution we propose, we must immediately

and seriously try to reject this decision, not defend it. Imaginary and multifaceted proposals must be carefully controlled and tested.”

Educator E. Glasser developed a critical thinking program that includes tests for reasoning, drawing conclusions, recognizing assumptions, assessing the strength of conclusions and arguments. In his opinion, critical thinking is the ability to assess the validity of reasoning, the degree of approval of actions and their justification, to find a specific limit to their application.

In the work of researchers in subsequent years (“second wave”), the concept of critical thinking is determined depending on the views of the authors. In particular,

David Kluster's definition of critical thinking consists of five points.

1. Each subject forms his own ideas, assessments and judgments independently of others. "No one can think critically for us, we do it only for ourselves." From this it can be concluded that only independent thinking can be critical.

2. Information is considered the starting point for the development of critical thinking, with its help motivation is created, without which a person cannot think critically.

3. Critical thinking begins with asking questions and understanding the problems that need to be solved. Preschool children should learn to understand the endless variety of problems that surround us and give them a critical assessment.

4. Critical thinking must be well-founded. Argumentation includes three main elements. The main element is a statement, that is, a thesis, a main idea or assumption. The statement is supported by a number of arguments.

5. Critical thinking is social thinking. Each theory is tested and expanded when shared with others. That is why scientific theories and ideas always require publications, as well as debates and discussions.

At first glance, based on the criteria set by D.Kluster, it may seem that critical thinking is no different from creative. To understand the difference, let's turn to the concept of the American psychologist G. Lindsey.

Critical thinking in the system of G. Lindsey is to test the proposed solutions, determine the scope of their application, and identify their shortcomings. Whereas creative thinking is aimed at creating new ideas. In order to identify truly useful, effective solutions, creative thinking must be supplemented with critical thinking. The purpose of critical thinking is to test the proposed ideas, that is, can they be applied?, how can they be improved?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. ONE of the most important cognitive aspect is critical thinking. In his life, child will face with problems which demands a solution. Resolve a problem is such a difficult thing to do in children, it includes such complicated thinking process, and before able to solve the problem, children need the ability to find the solution to their problem.

Critical thinking is ability to think about the problem and trying to solve it based on past experience, knowledge of logical judgment, and reasoning skill.

Critical thinking demands great effort to examine every conviction or assumptive knowledge based on evidence supporters and conclusions continued the result. Kids in particular tend to asked and curious about something, they will be asked and recheck for many times about it. Such when they see something move on the ground, they will asked what is it? Is it some kind of animal? Or is it something you can eat? They will ask you several time till they're sure with your answer. Such when they're meet a hole in the ground, they will ask what is it? Who make this hole, what the function of this hole, how can there's a hole in the ground. They will look for the answer, and recheck the answer for several times.

In old days, children will look for the answer in many possible ways, such as looking in the book, asking people around them or observing it several times and concluding the answer, but with technology this day such as smartphone or pc, they can type the word in search engine and get the answer. In the past, when people have family dinner or tea time, they will chat about random things, their children will ask some unexpected question and then will answer it together. Example: “why this table is round shape? Why do we use spoon or forks to eat, or why this fruit is some color or shape”? In the old day, they will try to answer the question together but now days what you need to do is open google and type the question you want to ask, and google will provide the answer for us. On one hand, it's such a great that we can get an answer for every question instantly about all the question that we had. On the other hand, it is also mean make our child lazy. They are no longer need effort to looking for the answer like their brain are freeze and unable to process all the information. Only with one click and the you get an answer.

We know in today society it is really rare to see a young kid read a book in public space such as station, train, hospital or somewhere else. If in the old day young kid used to read for pleasure than enhances their thinking instead they're use their smartphone to playing video game and watched their favorite tv show. This study followed the principles of qualitative and naturalistic research to describe and analyze the different aspects about critical thinking in preschoolers. The purpose was to provide a baseline that describes and analyzes the forms in which critical thinking is presented in the preschool classrooms. The study also focused on investigating

the view of the teachers about the importance of critical thinking for preschoolers. Three data collection instruments were selected: classroom observation, documents analysis and interviews. The variables taken into account for these techniques were the following: a) the presence of critical thinking in students, b) the incidence of teacher's instruction in the development of critical thinking and the presence of pedagogical strategies that promote critical thinking skills, and c) teachers' beliefs as to the importance of developing critical thinking in preschoolers.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. The process of determining the readiness of preschool children to demonstrate the basics of critical thinking in their behavior and educational activities is carried out at the identification stage. This stage includes the selection and development of tools for diagnosing the initial level of readiness of preschool children to develop critical thinking based on selected indicators (motivational, activity, reflective-evaluative), as well as the development of training and game programs for the development of critical thinking. This stage ended with a confirmatory experiment.

At the end of it, a formative experiment was organized: training and game programs for the development of critical thinking for children were completed with a control diagnosis that showed changes in the level of development of critical thinking in the experimental group and compared it with changes in the control group.

The following diagnostic procedures are used at the stages of identifying and controlling experiences: the methodology "Peculiarities of the manifestation of will in preschool children" (R.M. Gevorkyan), methods for assessing the level of formation of logical thinking (R.S. Nemov, S. D. Z Abramnaya), the method "Study of children's communication skills" (Yu.A. Afonkina, G.A. Uruntaeva), the technique "Reasoning skills" (E.S. Knyazeva).

Taking into account the results obtained in the process of theoretical analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature and the developed model for the development of critical thinking in the cognitive process of preschool children, an author's training and game program for

children aimed at developing critical thinking was developed. Thinking and teaching of preschool children were carried out in accordance with this program. The duration of the training was 10 months (from January to October), the results were obtained 45 minutes per week.

CONCLUSION. Initially, we can observe that at the beginning of the experiment, the levels of development of critical thinking in the cognitive process of the children in the experimental and control groups were almost the same, and at the end of the experiment, the results in the experimental group were higher. Now, we will analyze the results to assess the levels of development of critical thinking in the cognitive process of the children by each indicator.

1. Diagnostics of the level of development of critical thinking by the motivational criterion was carried out using the methodology of R.M. Gevorkya "Features of the manifestation of the will of preschool children".

Indicators of independence by which the level of independence of children is controlled:

- 1) organization of activities and actions without external help;
- 2) implementation of decisions without reminders;
- 3) the ability to defend one's opinion without being stubborn;
- 4) the ability to find something and organize one's own activities;
- 5) the ability to show initiative and creativity in solving emerging problems.

Each indicator is evaluated by points: if the indicator is rarely manifested in the child's behavior, then 1 point is given, if sometimes, then 2 points, if often or always, then 3 points.

5-8 points - low level;

9-13 points - average level;

14-15 points - high level.

2. Diagnostics of the level of formation of critical thinking by the activity criterion was carried out using the methods of assessing the level of formation of logical thinking by R.S. Nemov, S.D. Zabramnaya and Yu.A. Afonkina, G.A. Oruntaev "Study of children's communication skills".

0-24 - low level;

25-39 - average level;

40-50 - high level.

3. Y.A. Afonkina and G.A. Studying children's communication skills using Oruntaeva's methods.

Indicators by which the level of development of children's communication skills is monitored:

- 1) Do children know how to negotiate and come to a common decision;
- 2) Do they notice each other's deviations from the initial plan and how do they react to them;
- 3) How do they react to the result of the activity, to themselves and to their partners;
- 4) Do they help each other in the drawing process?
- 5) Do they know how to use the means of activity rationally.

Each indicator is evaluated by points:

0-1 - low level;

2-3 - average level;

4-5 - high level.

The conclusion about the level is made based on the sum of the points:

0-9 - low level;

10-19 - average level;

20-25 - high level

Summing up the results of the methods carried out, the level of development of critical thinking according to the activity criterion was determined.

The overall level is calculated as follows:

low level - a low level is determined or it prevails according to all criteria;

average level - an average level is determined or it prevails according to all criteria;

high - only a high level is determined or it prevails according to all criteria.

4) Diagnostics of the level of formation of critical thinking according to the reflective-evaluation criterion was carried out using the methodology of E.S. Knyazeva "Ability to reason".

The methodology assesses 3 parameters that make up readiness according to the reflective-evaluation criterion:

1) state;

2) action;

3) result.

Score (3 points for each element, if you have mastered it, 2 points, if you have almost mastered it, 1 point, if you have difficulties).

1. The correctness of the answers.

2. Did the child identify the contradiction in the task, is it possible to determine what is missing to resolve it?

3. Did you ask for help or clarification?

The level of readiness for the development of critical thinking was determined by the reflective-evaluation criterion.

The overall level is calculated as follows:

7-11 points - low level;

12-16 points - average level;

17-18 points - high level.

The overall level is calculated as follows:

low level - a low level is determined by all criteria or it prevails;

average level - an average level is determined by all criteria or it prevails;

high level - only a high level is determined by all criteria or it prevails.

Since the results of the experimental group in all criteria were higher than the results of the control group, it was statistically proven that mastery in the experimental groups significantly increased, and the level of development of critical thinking in the cognitive process of students in preschool educational organizations increased by 1.12 times, or an average of 12%.

REFERENCES

1. Paul R., Elder L. The Critical Thinking Reading and Writing Test Publisher: Foundation for Critical Thinking, 2006. – 68 p.
2. Халперн, Д. Психология критического мышления [Текст] / Д. Халперн. – 4-е международное издание. – СПб.: Питер, 2000. – 512 с
3. Монтень Мишель. Опыты. Избранные произведения в 3-х томах. Том 2. Пер. с фр. – Москва: «Педагогика», 1992. 560с.
4. Руссо Ж.Ж. «Эмиль или О воспитании». – Москва: 1995. С.62

5. Пиаже, Ж. Речь и мышление ребенка [Электронный ресурс] /Ж. Пиаже – 1994. – 528 с – Режим доступа: http://elibr.gnpbu.ru/text/piazhe_rech-myshlenie-rebenka_1994/go,0;fs,1/ [Дата обращения: 14 февраля 2018.
6. Скуднова Т.Д. Гуманистические традиции мировой социальной педагогики Таганрог. 2007.- 178 с.
7. Клустер Д. Что такое критическое мышление? // Критическое мышление и новые виды грамотности. – М.: ЦГЛ, 2005. – С. 5-13
8. Темпл Ч., Стил Дж.Л., Мередит К.С. Критическое мышление – углубленная методика. Пос. 4. – М.: Изд-во Инта «Открытое общество», 1998.
9. Халперн, Д. Психология критического мышления [Текст] / Д. Халперн. – 4-е международное издание. – СПб.: Питер, 2000. – 512 с.
10. Хухлаева, О.В. В каждом ребенке – солнце? Родителям о детской психологии [Текст] / О.В. Хухлаева. – М.: Академический проект, 2017. – 314 с.
11. Georg Christoph Lichtenberg. Physikvorlesung. Nach J.Chr. P. Erxlebens Anfangsgründen der Naturlehre. Aus den Erinnerungen von Gottlieb Gamauf, bearbeitet und mit einer Einleitung versehen von Fritz Krafft, marixverlag Wiesbaden 2007.